

Hearing aid use and the risk of dementia diagnosis in UK Biobank: a comment on Machado-Fragua et al. (Nature Aging, 2025)

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Abstract

Hearing loss has been associated with cognitive decline and research on hearing aids and dementia represents a valuable avenue to explore mechanistic hypotheses. In contrast to most research on this topic, studies in UK Biobank, including one recently published in Nature Aging by Machado-Fragua et al., found a positive association between hearing aid use and the risk of a dementia diagnosis. Here we critique the above work by pointing out that (1) assertions in the paper of other studies showing the above link are misleading, (2) there is insufficient evidence for some of the claims made by the authors, especially that confounding through hearing loss severity can explain the positive association, and (3) previous work offers an alternative explanations for the findings.

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Introduction

We read with interest the recently published paper by Machado-Fragua and colleagues, in which the authors conducted analyses on hearing loss (HL), hearing aid (HA) use, and dementia in two longitudinal cohorts: the Whitehall II study, and UK Biobank (UKB)¹. While the results from the former were mostly null, analyses from UKB suggested an increased risk of dementia in both people with HL and in those using HAs – when compared with either healthy controls or participants with HL who were non-users of HAs. Some recent studies have highlighted the role of hearing loss (HL) as a risk factor for dementia^{2,3} and the potential utility of hearing aids (HA) to improve hearing and – in the case of a causal link – to prevent dementia⁴. Machado-Fragua et al. have conducted careful analyses on an important topic, and we found the side-by-side analyses from two separate cohorts insightful. Still, we would like to offer some critique of the paper and highlight some omitted previous work.

Previous findings

The authors referred to two earlier findings on the positive association between HA use and dementia. One of the two cited studies found an increased rate of dementia in participants with HL who were users of HAs (HR=1.06, 95% CI=1.01-1.10) and in those that were not (1.20, 1.13-1.27), but both in reference to people without HL⁵. The other found a higher rate of dementia in people with HL that did not use HAs (95% CI=1.40-1.86 and 1.57-2.52 for “insufficient” and “poor” hearing, respectively), but no statistically significant effect in people with HL that used HAs (0.80-1.95 and 0.74-1.99) – again, compared to people with normal hearing⁶. Any treatment to address an existing modifiable risk factor for dementia is unlikely to result in a full recovery and its associated risk for the disease should not be compared with a group unexposed to the risk factor. It is true that both studies found a higher rate of dementia in HA users when compared to those without HL, but both results suggest a *protective* effect of HA use in people with HL. One of the few studies that indeed found a detrimental effect of HA use in people with HL (RR=1.43, 95% CI=1.08-1.88 over a 12.4-year follow-up), was one that we conducted and published last year⁷. In that study we also drew upon UKB data, used a more restrictive criterion for self-reported HL ascertainment than Machado-Fragua et al., additionally employed the electronic healthcare record to detect the exposure, more explicitly controlled for the confounding effects of healthcare utilisation, and studied the effects of HA use specifically among those with incident HL. Due to more restrictions, our sample was smaller than in the study by Machado-Fragua et al., and our estimates were less precise. Our results were similar to those by Machado-Fragua et al., and we agree with the authors in their assessment that the associations are unlikely to be causal. The findings are at odds with most of the literature on the topic and we see no credible mechanism that would result in such a substantial increase in dementia risk with HA use.

Interpretation of results

Seemingly to temper the finding of a potential harm by HAs, the authors additionally stratified the sample by length of follow-up, where they found a higher estimate for the effect of HA use on dementia for participants with ≤ 10 years of follow-up (HR=1.32, 95% CI: 1.16-1.51) than in those with >10 years (1.18, 1.05-1.34). However, compared to the contrast in the group of participants with shorter follow-up, the contrast in the group with longer follow-up was conducted on a selected, less susceptible group of participants (because the more susceptible will have had experienced dementia). Such selection bias, along with changes in adherence to HA use over time, could explain the lower rate observed in that stratum, even if HA use did increase the risk of dementia. To interpret the seemingly puzzling result for the HA-dementia link, the authors suggest confounding through HL severity, but we see no evidence for that in their paper. Upon adjustment for HL severity, the precision of the estimate decreased and was no longer significant, but the HR for HA use *increased* from 1.34 (95% CI=1.04-1.74) to 1.40 (0.96-2.04). We would also encourage Machado-Fragua et al. to clearly distinguish between rates and risks. They sometimes refer to HR estimates as “risk estimates”, erroneously write that a meta-analysis³ reported RRs (it reported HRs), and directly compare their HR estimates to RRs from another study⁸ without noting the distinction. The hazard is an instantaneous rate, whereas the risk is a cumulative probability of occurrence within a certain period. The two coincide under certain conditions, but they are conceptually – and often empirically – different.

Alternative explanations

We offer two alternative explanations to the ones offered by the authors, both of which we explicated in our previous publication⁷. First, there may be some confounding by healthcare contact/utilisation. We showed that HA users were more likely to access healthcare, frequent healthcare contact was associated with the risk of a dementia diagnosis, and that adjustment for the number of inpatient and GP visits reduced the estimates for the effect of HA on dementia risk. Machado-Fragua et al. also adjusted their models for the number of chronic conditions which may have captured healthcare utilisation, and the effect of HA persisted. Second, not (only) HL severity, but HL timing might play a role. In our study, we found most of the trend for the dementia ~ HA association to be driven by participants whose HL was detected relatively early (through the healthcare record before study baseline). Those people were more likely to report the use of HAs during the UKB assessment. It is tempting to assume a sensitive period for the effect of HL on dementia, but these participants may also represent a more vulnerable group and one in which the occurrence of common causes of HL and dementia was more likely. It is worth noting that neither of the two UKB studies explicitly handled the competing risk of death with a cumulative-incidence

approach. Machado-Fragua et al. stated that they “took competing risks into account” but they – like us – used cause-specific Cox models that simply censored deaths. In our study, mortality was higher in HA users than non-users (8.8% vs 5.8%) and any informative censoring would bias the dementia estimate *towards the null*, not away from it. This makes it unlikely that the observed excess risk is an artefact of unaccounted competing risks and reinforces our suggestion that in this sample HA users constitute a more vulnerable group.

Conclusion

As far as we are aware, such strong positive estimates for the association between HA use and dementia in people with HL as described by us⁷ and Machado-Fragua et al.¹ have among large-scale prospective studies been reported only in UKB. We do not know why this is the case, and we encourage others to probe whether the non-representativeness of the sample, the means of exposure ascertainment, or some other peculiarity of UKB may be causing these results.

Competing interests

None to declare.

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